

Photocatalytic degradation of sulfamethoxazole with Co-CuS@TiO₂ heterostructures under solar light irradiation

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ABSTRACT

This work describes a successful approach to dope copper sulfide with different amounts of Co²⁺ ions and combine it with TiO₂ through a simple one-step hydrothermal process. Compared with the bare CuS, the synthesized Co-CuS@TiO₂ heterostructures promote charge transport and restrict the recombination of photoexcited electrons and holes. The intrinsic properties of Co-CuS@TiO₂ samples are systematically examined through experimental characterizations and density functional theory (DFT) theoretical calculations. Photocatalytic degradation tests under simulated solar light irradiation were performed using sulfamethoxazole degradation as a model emerging persistent antibiotic. The photocatalytic performance was enhanced after cobalt doping, and the heterostructure doped with 3% of Co exhibited the best degradation with an apparent rate constant of 0.0216 min⁻¹. This sample also showed a much faster settling than bare TiO₂, which indicates a much easier separation of the reaction media after being used. The enhancement of degradation is attributed to the increased light absorption and the more efficient charge transfer and separation. The plausible photocatalytic degradation mechanism of sulfamethoxazole was also proposed. This study presents a novel strategy to prepare potential photocatalysts for the elimination of emerging pollutants.